

Practice Abstract #2

Climate-Resilient Orchard and Mountain Farming: Insights from the Greek Co-Creation Workshop in Zagora

Summary

OBJECTIVES. On 13 June 2025, EARTHONE held a workshop in Zagora (Greece) that brought together farmers, cooperative representatives, advisors, researchers and local authorities to identify the main needs of orchard growers and mountain farmers facing strong climate variability. The aim was to explore how EARTHONE tools could support decisions on irrigation, soil management, pest risks and long-term orchard sustainability.

RESULTS. Participants highlighted that rapid temperature changes, increased pest pressure, water shortages and storm damage in the Pelion area strongly affect yields of apples, chestnuts and other tree crops.

Figure 1. The organising team behind the EARTHONE co-creation workshop in Greece.

Figure 2. The questionnaire used during the workshop.

They saw strong potential in using local microclimate data, including frequent weather observations and soil moisture monitoring, and in combining sensor data with historical cooperative records. The Scenario Builder was considered useful for evaluating orchard management strategies under extreme weather, while the Information Factory was valued for centralising data and providing early warnings for pests and fungal diseases.

PRACTICAL IMPLICATIONS. A practical entry point is targeted monitoring using weather, humidity and soil moisture sensors to improve irrigation planning and anticipate risks. Main costs relate to sensor installation in steep orchards, while benefits include reduced water use and earlier risk detection. Collective use through cooperatives can lower costs, reduce learning efforts and support long-term adoption.

Additional information

Figure 3. During the workshop in Zagora

Implementation in mountainous Greek farming systems depends on strong local coordination and shared infrastructure. A major facilitating factor is the tradition of cooperative-based farming in Zagora. Growers in that region routinely exchange knowledge and rely on collective decision-making for harvest scheduling, pest control, and market planning. This structure enables faster adoption of digital tools, as responsibilities can be shared and costs distributed. Local advisory services, including agronomists embedded in the cooperative, can help translate tool outputs into practical orchard actions.

However, many orchards are located on steep slopes with limited access to electricity and connectivity, making sensor deployment physically challenging. Weather stations are sparse, and microclimates vary sharply even within short distances, creating a need for fine-scale data to avoid misleading recommendations. Farmers also expressed concern about the reliability of long-term predictions, as extreme events (e.g. hail, frost, sudden heatwaves) have increased unpredictably. Ensuring that EARTHONE's tools incorporate local experiential knowledge and historical cooperative records will be critical to build trust.

Future actions should test the tools across different orchard altitudes to evaluate performance under variable conditions. More information is needed on linking humidity and canopy data with real-time fungal disease models, which would directly benefit fruit growers. Farmers are encouraged to begin with small-scale pilot plots to build confidence and gradually expand usage. Stable support frameworks, training tailored to cooperative structures, and locally adapted interfaces will be essential to ensure long-lasting impact.

Useful links: [Blog-EARTHONE workshop in Greece advances tool co-design for apple cultivation](#)

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